

Unification of treatments and interventions for tinnitus patients

Proposal No.: 848261

Deliverable D2.3: Report on Gender and Equal Opportunities

Deliverable No. D8 – WP2

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Target Dissemination Level	Public
Status of the Document	Version 2

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1 Introduction

In science, gender equity leaves a remaining issue. The UNESCO Institute for Statistics identified that less than 30% of researchers worldwide are women¹. In (South-Eastern) Europe, only 4 out of 41 countries achieved gender parity. In 2021/22, around two thirds of medical students in Germany were women.² Unfortunately, no figures could be found across Europe, but one can assume that the proportion of women among medical students is also higher across Europe than that of men. Yet women are (or seem) still underrepresented in research.³ This deliverable will provide gender-distributed data on the project workforce, on the impact of the working environment and on the career and professional mobility.

2 Gender Balance

2.1 First Quarter 2020 - Preparation

At the start of the project, we asked the consortium members about the planned composition of their team, the gender balance and the tasks and duties of the team members (without administrative staff like Grant Manager and legal representatives, see Table 1. The overall gender distribution at this time was 44.44% women.

At that time, the expected proportion of women from areas other than research was comparatively high, more women than men were busy with administrative matters concerning the RCT and the preparations for the RCT itself (Figure 1).

The proportion of female researchers who were involved in creating for example the statistical analysis plan, the study protocol or the study documents was comparatively low. Regarding the Principal Investigators, four out of 13 consortium partners or their deputies were women.

¹ <https://uis.unesco.org/sites/default/files/documents/fs55-women-in-science-2019-en.pdf>

² <https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/200758/umfrage/entwicklung-der-anzahl-der-medizinstudenten/>

³ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-022-04966-w>

	Male researchers	Female researchers	Male other than researchers	Female other than researchers	Total number employees	Total number women	% women
	2020	2020	2020	2020	2020		
UHREG	7	1	2	3	13	4	30.76
KUL	1	2	1	3	7	5	71.43
UOA	2	1	1	1	5	2	40
CHA	1	2	0	3	6	5	83.33
SAS/GRA	3	0	1	1	5	1	20
KI	1	0	1	1	3	1	33.33
OVGU (=MAG)	2	1	2	5	10	6	60
UKW	3	0	0	0	3	0	0
ICCS	3	4	3	0	10	4	40
MIL	1	1	3	1	6	2	33.33
VIL	2	0	3	2	7	2	28.75
SPX	1	1	0	0	2	1	50
ZEI/Excelya	1	3	0	0	4	3	75
	28	16	17	20	81	36	
	34.56%	19.75%	21.00%	24.70%			44.44%

Table 1 estimated gender distribution first quarter 2020

Gender distribution at the first quarter of 2020

Figure 1 estimated gender distribution at the first quarter of 2020

The study centers Berlin, DE (CHA: 83.3%) and Leuven, BE (KUL: 71.4) estimated a comparatively high proportion of women in their team: the lack of women in the team at the University Hospital in Wuerzburg (UKW) was attributed to the transfer of the PI from Ulm to Wuerzburg shortly before the start of the project and slightly improved during the UNITI project. In general the gender distribution in the field of informatic engineering - like in Wuerzburg - is still low.

2.2 First and Second Funding Period – Conduction of the RCT

The number of team members varied in some of the centres, – some members were hired not right at the beginning of the project, some members already left the project after a short time. Shortly before the start of the RCT the teams reached their final numbers of employees. Encouragingly, the proportion of women in the project has also increased again with the new appointments, namely to 46.7%. In 7 out of 13 project partners, exactly or more than half of the colleagues were female; the Charité Center in Berlin, DE, even recorded a 100% share of women (Table 2).

	Male researchers	Female researchers	male other than researchers	female other than researchers	total	women	%
	2020-22	2020-22	2020-22	2020-22	2020-22		
UHREG	3	2	4	6	14	8	53.33
KUL	2	1	1	1	5	2	40.0
UOA	4	5	0	0	9	5	55.56
CHA	0	3	0	0	3	3	100.0
Genyo	4	6	4	1	15	7	46.67
KI	1	2	0	0	3	2	66.67
OVGU (=MAG)	4	2	0	0	6	2	33.33
UKW	8	1	0	0	9	1	11.11
ICCS	9	5	0	0	14	5	35.7
MIL	1	2	0	0	3	2	50.0
VIL	2	1	0	0	3	1	33.33
SPHYNX	1	2	0	0	3	2	66.67
Excelya	1	2	0	0	3	2	66.67
	40	34	9	8	90	42	
	44.4%	37.8%	10.0%	8.9%			46.7%

Table 2 gender distribution first and second funding period 2020-22

Figure 2 gender distribution during the project 2020-22

2.3 Third Funding Period – End of Study, End of Project March 2023*

Although there were personnel changes within the teams towards the end of the project, the proportion of women in the overall project remained unchanged at 46.7% (see Table 3).

*The date of the original end of the project, March 31, 2023, is decisive for the survey. Many of the scientific contracts concluded within the framework of UNITI were limited until March 31, 2023, and could not be extended due to legal restrictions and a lack of financial resources.

	Male researchers	Female researchers	male other than researchers	female other than researchers	total	women	%
	2023	2023	2023	2023	2023		
UHREG	3	2	4	9	18	11	61.11%
KUL	4	3	0		7	3	42.87%
UOA	4	5	0	0	9	5	55.56%
CHA	0	2	0	0	2	2	100.0%
Genyo	4	6	4	1	15	7	46.67%
KI	1	2	0	0	3	2	66.67%
OVGU (=MAG)	4	2	2	0	8	2	25.0%
UKW	8	1	0	0	9	1	11.11%
ICCS	9	5	0	0	14	5	35.7%
MIL	1	1	0	0	1	1	50.0%
VIL	2	1	0	0	3	1	33.33%
SPHYNX	1	3	0	0	4	3	75.0%
Excelya	0	2	1	0	3	2	66.67%
	41	35	11	10	97	45	
	42.3%	36.08%	11.3%	10.3%			
women in total						46.7%	

Table 3 gender distribution last funding period until 03/2023

Figure 3 gender distribution at the end of the project 2023

In comparison to the other consortium partners, UKW is clearly lagging behind with a proportion of women of 11.11%. The task of the consortium partner UKW mainly consisted of software programming, that is merging the existing apps (diary and Shades of Noise) with psychoeducational components that were still to be developed, to the UNITI-App.

2.4 Development of the Proportion of Women in the Project

During the course of the project, the proportion of both female and male researchers increased, with the proportion of female researchers even rising significantly by more than 16.2%. The proportion of male and female persons other than researchers decreased considerably (male -9.7%, female -14.4%).

	Male researchers		Female researchers		male other than researchers		female other than researchers		total		women	
	2020	2023	2020	2023	2020	2023	2020	2023	2020	2023	2020	2023
UHREG	7	3	1	2	2	4	3	9	13	18	4	11
KUL	1	4	2	3	1	0	3		7	7	5	3
UOA	2	4	1	5	1	0	1	0	5	9	2	5
CHA	1	0	2	2	0	0	3	0	3	2	3	2
Genyo	3	4	0	6	1	4	1	1	5	15	1	7
KI	1	1	0	2	1	0	1	0	3	3	1	2
OVGU (=MAG)	2	4	1	2	2	2	5	0	10	8	6	2
UKW	3	8	0	1	0	0	0	0	3	9	0	1
ICCS	3	9	4	5	3	0	0	0	10	9	4	4
MIL	1	1	1	1	3	0	1	0	6	2	2	1
VIL	2	2	0	1	3	0	2	0	7	3	2	1
SPHYNX	1	1	1	3	0	0		0	2	3	1	3
Excelya	1	0	3	2	0	1	0	0	4	3	3	2
	28	41	16	35	17	11	20	10	78	97	34	45
	34.6%	42.3%	19.8%	36.08%	21.0%	11.3%	24.7%	10.3%				
women in total											43.59%	46.7%

Table 4 comparison of gender distribution in UNITI 2020 – 2023

2.5 Gender Distribution between “Researchers” and “Other than Researchers” in 2023

A clear distinction between women and men as researchers or as “other than researcher” is only possible to a limited degree. While some team members can be clearly assigned to the “other than researchers” category – such as hearing care professionals or audiologists – a clear assignment to the “researcher” category is not always possible since some people in the teams worked in both categories, such as the project coordinators, the study nurses or study coordinators for example.

While the proportion of men and women in the “other than researchers” group varies by only one percentage point, the overall view of the UNITI Consortium shows differences among the “researchers” group. Splitting this group into “senior researchers” - post docs, PIs or researchers whose PhD was more than 7 years ago - and PhD students, the proportion of women among senior researchers is 5% lower than that of male (senior) researchers. The proportion of female PhD students also differs from that of male doctoral students by only one percentage point (see Table 5).

Center	PIs female ⁴	senior female	senior male	junior female	junior male	others than researchers female	others than researchers male
UHREG			0	2	3	9	4
KUL	1	1	2	2	2		
UOA			1	5	3		
CHA	1	0		2			
SAS/GRA		4	2	2	2	1	4
KI		0	1	2			
OVGU (=MAG)	1	0	1	2	3		2
UKW			5	1	3		
ICCS		3	4	2	5		
MIL				1	1		
VIL			2	1			
SPH		3			1		
ZEI (Excelya)	1	2					1
		13	18	22	23	10	11
		13.4%	18.7%	22.7%	23.7%	10.3%	11.3%

Table 5 gender distribution between “researchers” and “others than researchers” in 2023”

⁴ The PIs of CHA and OVGU (=MAG) were not paid by the UNITI-project

UHREG provided by far the largest team, which is probably also due to its role as project leader. Among the members of the Regensburg team paid via the UNITI project, there was no senior researcher, but three male junior researchers and two female PhD students. In order to be able to handle the diverse, cross-center tasks, UHREG also employed the largest number of research and/or student assistants, with all of the student assistants being female. Two male scientific and/or student assistants were also employed at OVGU (=MAG).

2.6 Women at Various Hierarchical Levels

Looking at the number of women in the role of the PI, the UNITI project approximately reflects the actual situation of women in leadership positions at universities and higher education institutions (2021: 27%⁵), or is slightly above at 30.77% - at only four centres the PI was female.

Center	PI (% female)	Senior (incl. PI) (% female)	PhD (% female)	Other than researchers (% female)	Student Assistants (% female)
UHREG			100%	69.3%	100%
KUL	100%	33.3%	50%		
UOA			62.5%		
CHA	100%	100%	100%		
SAS/GRA		66.7%	50%	20%	
KI			100%		
OVGU (=MAG)	100%		66.7%		
UKW			25%		
ICCS		21.4%	14.3%		
MIL			100%		
VIL		33.3%			
SPH		75.0%			
ZEI (Excelya)	100%	100%			

Table 6 proportion of women at various hierarchical levels per centre

3 Working Environment, Scientific Career and Professional Mobility

The corona pandemic has brought major restrictions on public life. Curfews, bans on contact, the maintenance of safety distances and strict hygiene regulations posed particular challenges for the UNITI managers, especially when conducting the clinical study.

On the one hand, this meant additional work for face-to-face appointments as part of the clinical study - due to the additional work involved in testing the patients before and in disinfecting the premises and equipment after the visit. On the other hand, some work that had to be done as part of the clinical study could also be relocated to the home office (sending questionnaires via e-mail, contacting patients via study mobile phones or e-mail, interim evaluations, data quality

⁵ <https://www.destatis.de/DE/Themen/Gesellschaft-Umwelt/Bildung-Forschung-Kultur/Hochschulen/Tabellen/frauenanteile-akademischelaufbahn.html>

checks, exports, analyses...). Family, children and everyday duties could be reconciled much better this way. Thus, the researchers with family (predominantly but not exclusively) who were not involved in the conduct of the study took advantage of the opportunity to work almost exclusively at home and to participate in regular meetings via Zoom or Teams. (Eventually) long journeys to work were no longer necessary or even not allowed due to the strict corona requirements that were applied in the clinics - time that ultimately benefited the actual research work.

In a survey on the experiences of employees with home office during the Corona pandemic, "77% of those surveyed opionated that the home office makes it easier to combine work and family. 60% believe that they can organize work at home even more effectively than in the office. However, 60% of those surveyed who work from home have the impression that the boundaries between work and leisure are blurring."⁶

Even after the pandemic, many of the colleagues with home office experience continued to work from home.

4 Conclusion

The gender distribution in the UNITI consortium improved during the project period. Considering the overall gender distribution of all UNITI members, a ratio of 46.7% was reached at the end of the project. However, it has to be mentioned that a closer look at different job categories and different research disciplines reveals imbalances that still exist:

The area of app and database development still tends to be a male domain, whereas women are found in equal numbers in testing and first and second level support - these tasks were also predominantly done in the home office.

A greater number of women were responsible for the successful completion of the RCT. Thus, there were a total of 28 women who performed the examinations and questionnaire surveys during the study visits, compared with 15 men with the same tasks. In contrast, there were only 2 women versus 8 men who performed the hearing aid fittings. In turn, almost twice as many women than men (14 : 8), were responsible for data entry as well as for data quality check and analysis at the end of the study.

In any case, it is gratifying that during the project period very many (but not only) women from different fields - psychology, medicine, biology, bioinformatics - were motivated to do work in a multidisciplinary team and to strive for a PhD.

The fact that the proportion of women in the consortium increased during the project period and did not change, especially towards the end, is encouraging, but should not obscure the fact that it is still mainly men who hold the leading positions, but mainly women who "keep such a project running" or ensure its successful completion.

⁶ <https://www.boeckler.de/de/boeckler-impuls-homeoffice-besser-klar-geregelt-27643.htm>